

Potentiometric Studies of Stepwise Chelate Formation of Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Mn(II) with Vanillin-Anthranilate (Van-An)

PURUSHOTTAM B. CHAKRAWARTI and PRAMILA KHANNA

Chemical Laboratories, M. L. B. Girls College, Bhopal-462 001

Manuscript received 4 January 1984, accepted 25 March 1984

Interaction of vanillin-anthranilate (Van-An) with some transition metal ions, Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Mn(II) in 20% aqueous ethanolic solution has been studied potentiometrically. Stepwise proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation constants have been evaluated at 30 and 40° and at a fixed ionic strength of 0.1M KNO₃. The thermodynamic parameters, ΔG , ΔH and ΔS evaluated at 30° and 0.1 M KNO₃ ionic strength show that the reaction of Van-An in solution with these metal ions is an endothermic reaction and entropy change plays an important part in giving the observed order of stability as Fe(III) > Cu(II) > Ni(II) > Co(II) > Mn(II).

AN extensive work has been done¹⁻³ on metal chelates of Schiff bases derived from a variety of aldehydes and amines. The Schiff bases derived from amino acids are known to play an important role in biological reactions⁴. Little work has been done to study the interaction of transition metal ions with the Schiff bases of amino acids, particularly with those derived from Vanillin. In continuation of our attempt to study metal chelates of certain Schiff bases derived from Vanillin⁵⁻⁷, the present communication reports the results of our study of the interaction of transition metal ions, Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Mn(II), with Van-An in a 20% aq. ethanol at 30 and 40° and at a constant ionic strength, I=0.1 M KNO₃, using Calvin-Bjerrum's pH-titration technique as adapted by Irving and Rossotti⁹.

Experimental

The ligand Van-An was prepared and purified by the procedure described earlier⁶. All other reagents were of A.R. or of high purity grade. The preparation and standardisation of the metal ion solutions and the experimental details remain the same as given elsewhere⁷.

Stoichiometry of the various species formed in solution was traced using conductometric titrations, and the proton-ligand and the metal-ligand stability constants were computed by Bjerrum-Calvin pH titration as adapted by Irving-Rossotti⁹. This involves titration of the following thermostated mixtures of solution in 20% (v/v) ethanol-water medium with a carbonate free 0.1 M KOH in the same solvent medium :

(a) 5 ml 0.1 M HNO₃, (b) Mixture (a) + 10 ml 0.01 M Van-An solution, (c) Mixture (b) + 5 ml 0.002 M metal solution.

Titration were carried out in a specially designed 100 ml cell having an outer jacket for circulation of water at a fixed temperature. The cell had a plastic lid with appropriate holes to accommodate the electrodes, burette nozzle and nitrogen bubbling device.

The ionic strength of the above solutions was maintained constant at 0.1 M using requisite amount of KNO₃. Correction of pH in 20% ethanol-water system was done as described by Van-Uitert and Hass¹⁰ and Irving and Rossotti⁹.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry : Conductometric titrations (Fig. 1) indicate formation of ML and ML₂ complexes with

Fig. 1. Conductometric titrations, Van-An systems [A] Mn(II), [B] Co(II), [C] Ni(II), [D] Cu(II) and [E] Fe(III).

Van-An and the metal ions used. The maximum value of \bar{n} (~ 2) (Fig. 3) also confirm the formation of two complexes, ML and ML₂.

Further, pH-titrations reveal that in all the systems studied only one proton is released during complexation of each molecule of Van-An. Thus the reactions may be represented as

where, $M^{n+} = Co^{2+}, Ni^{2+}, Cu^{2+}, Mn^{2+}$ or Fe^{3+} and $H_2L = Van-An$, with two replaceable hydrogen atoms.

Proton-ligand formation constants $\log K_n^H$: pH titration curve in case of the ligand showed two inflections, one at pH ~ 4 and the other at pH ~ 7 , with consumption of two equivalents of alkali per mole of the ligand Van-An. This indicates two successive steps of its acid dissociation, which can be represented by the Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

The stepwise proton-ligand formation constants, $\log K_n^H$, at the two temperatures 30 and 40° were obtained by (a) the half integral method from the plot of $\bar{n}A$ (the average number of proton associated with Van-An) vs pH, (b) the pointwise calculation using the equations

$$\log K_1^H = pH + \log \frac{\bar{n}A}{1 - \bar{n}A}$$

and
$$\log K_2^H = pH + \log \frac{2 - \bar{n}A}{1 - \bar{n}A}$$

Fig 2. Proton ligand stability constants.
 —○— 30°
 —●— 40°.

and (c) the linear plot method. The results obtained are recorded in Table 1 (Fig. 2) and are found in agreement.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF VAN-AN AT 30° AND 40°, AND 0.1 M (KNO₃) IONIC STRENGTH

	30°	40°	Method
Log K_1^H	4.20	4.20	a
	4.20	4.20	b
	4.20 (4.20)	4.20 (4.20)	c
Log K_2^H	6.75	7.17	a
	6.76	7.19	b
	6.75 (6.75)	7.19 (7.15)	c
Log β_2^H	10.95	11.37	a
	10.96	11.39	b
	10.95 (10.95)	11.30 (10.35)	c

a, Half integral method ; b, point-wise calculation ; c, linear plot method.

The values of $\bar{n}A$, at different pH were calculated using the formula of Irving and Rossotti⁹

$$\bar{n}A = Y - \frac{(v'' - v')(N^0 + E^0)}{(v^0 + v') \cdot TCL^0}$$

where, v' and v'' are the volumes of alkali required to reach the same pH in the acid and the ligand titrations curves, respectively while v^0 , TCL^0 , E^0 and N^0 are the initial volume of the mixture, initial concentrations of the ligand, initial concentration of the acid and the concentration of titrant, respectively. Y is the number of dissociable protons.

Metal ligand formation constants, $\log K_n$: In the stepwise complex formation, the nth metal-ligand stability constant, K_n , is given by

$$K_n = \frac{CML_n}{CML_{n-1} \cdot CL}$$

For plotting formation curves, graph between average number of ligand bound to metal (\bar{n}) and free ligand exponent (PL), \bar{n} and PL values were obtained using equations⁹

$$\bar{n} = \frac{(v^{III} - v^{II})(N^0 + E^0)}{(v^0 + v^{II}) \cdot \bar{n}A \cdot TCM^0}$$

$$PL = \log_{10} \left[\frac{\sum_{n=0}^{n-j} \beta_n^H \left(\frac{1}{\text{anti log } B} \right)^n}{TCL^0 - \bar{n} \cdot TCM^0} \cdot \frac{v^0 + v^{III}}{v^0} \right]$$

where, TCM^0 is total concentration of metal ions, B is the pH, β_n^H is overall proton ligand constant and v^{III} is the volume of alkali required to reach the same pH in metal titration curve, while the other terms have their usual meaning.

The values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were recorded directly from the formation curves (Fig. 3). The refined values were obtained by the best least square fit. The results obtained at two temperatures, 30

and 40°, are given in Table 2. At 40°, the formation curve in case of Fe(III) did not permit the value of K_1 , hence the same was obtained by least square method.

Fig. 3. Formation curves Van-An systems, —○— 30°, —□— 40°; [A] Mn(II), [B] Co(II), [C] Ni(II), [D] Cu(II) and [E] Fe(III).

TABLE 2—STEPWISE FORMATION OF VAN-AN COMPLEXES AT 30° AND 40° AND 0.1 M (KNO₃) IONIC STRENGTH

Metal ions	30°			40°		
	Log K ₁	Log K ₂	Log β ₂	Log K ₁	Log K ₂	Log β ₂
Fe(III)	6.68 (6.83)	5.04 (5.10)	11.72 (11.93)	— (7.32)	5.62 (5.62)	— (12.94)
Cu(II)	6.16 (5.99)	3.86 (3.95)	10.02 (9.94)	6.46 (6.46)	4.04 (4.17)	10.50 (10.63)
Ni(II)	5.60 (5.51)	3.48 (3.48)	9.08 (8.99)	5.90 (5.98)	3.55 (3.52)	9.45 (9.50)
Co(II)	5.48 (5.37)	3.28 (3.26)	8.76 (8.63)	5.62 (5.74)	3.43 (3.30)	9.05 (9.05)
Mn(II)	5.18 (5.06)	3.14 (3.16)	8.32 (8.16)	5.58 (5.60)	3.32 (3.23)	8.90 (8.84)

The values in paranthesis are obtained by the best least square fit.

The nature of the pH titration curves in the absence and in the presence of the metal ions indicates that the first step acid dissociation of Van-An (i.e. deprotonation of the COOH group) is influenced by the metal ions. pH range (3.5-6.5). Thus considering the pK_{COOH} value of Van-An, stepwise complex formation of these metal ions with Van-An molecules may be assumed to take place through deprotonation of the carboxyl group (Scheme 2).

Thus the phenolic hydrogen of the ligand is retained with the chelates. This is clear from the metal titration curves which show liberation of more than one equivalent of acid per gram ion of the metal at pH greater than 7 i.e. after $\bar{n}=2$, which

may be accounted for by assuming stepwise acid dissociation of the ML^2 chelate.

Scheme 2

Further, from the analysis of the formation curves (Fig. 3) it is clear that the complex formation by Van-An follows the same sequence as found for the amino acids¹¹. First, one atom of the metal combined with one molecule of Van-An. The 1 : 1 complex thus formed did not appreciably combine with a second molecule of Van-An to give the 1 : 2 complex, until more than 80% of the 1 : 1 complex had formed, indicating that the formation of the two species is independent of each other.

The order of stability obtained in this study shows that Van-An, like the amino-acids¹¹ exhibits the usual relative avidities for these metal ions as

which follow the Irving-Williams series¹² and the empirical rules¹³.

However, the values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were found to increase with the increasing temperature in accordance with the values of $\log K_{\bar{n}}^H$ for the ligand indicating that the higher temperature (40°) favours the formation of the ligand and the metal complexes.

Thermodynamic parameters: The thermodynamic parameters computed for the complexation reactions studied are the changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) and have been calculated using the isotherm, the isobar and the Gibbs-Helmholtz's equations¹⁴, respectively at 30° and at an ionic strength of 0.1 M KNO₃. The values are tabulated in Table 3.

A perusal of the thermodynamic parameters (Table 3) clearly indicates that the reactions studied in this investigation are all endothermic (in confirmation with the metal-ligand formation constants). Thus, the $T\Delta S$ term is large enough to outweigh the $+\Delta H$ term of these endothermic reactions. The very high values of entropy change for these complex forming reactions probably indicate that complete chelation extensively alters solvation of the

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC CONSTANTS OF VAN-AN COMPLEXES OF CERTAIN TRANSITION METALS AT 30° AND 0.1 M (KNO₃) IONIC STRENGTH

		Fe(III)	Cu(II)	Ni(II)	Co(II)	Mn(II)
Free energy change	$-\Delta G_1$	9.52	8.36	7.69	7.49	7.06
	$-\Delta G_2$	7.12	5.52	4.85	4.55	4.33
Enthalpy change kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta G$	16.65	13.38	12.55	12.05	11.39
	$-\Delta H_1$	21.80	20.61	20.31	16.34	23.78
	$-\Delta H_2$	22.53	9.61	1.83	1.82	5.79
	$-\Delta H$	43.94	30.19	22.14	18.14	29.56
Entropy change cal deg ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S_1$	103.4	95.6	92.4	70.5	101.8
	$-\Delta S_2$	97.8	49.9	22.0	21.0	33.4
	$-\Delta S$	199.9	145.4	114.4	93.6	135.1

various species. This is quite in accordance with the ionic interaction between the metal cation and the vanillin-anthranilate anion.

References

1. R. N. HOLM, G. W. EVERETT, JR. and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Progr. Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 7, 83.
2. L. SACCONI, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1966, 1, 126.
3. S. YMADA, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1966, 1, 415.
4. A. L. LEHNINGER, "Biochemistry", Worth Pub., N. Y., 1975.
5. P. B. CHAKRAWARTI and P. KHANNA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 59, 828.
6. P. B. CHAKRAWARTI and P. KHANNA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 60, 1030.
7. P. B. CHAKRAWARTI and P. KHANNA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, 61, 112.
8. A. E. MARTELL and M. CALVIN, "Chemistry of Metal Chelate Compounds" Printice Hall, N. Y., p. 192.
9. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
10. L. G. VAN UITERT and C. HASS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 3651.
11. A. ALBERT, *Biochem. J.*, 1950, 47, 531.
12. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *Nature*, 1948, 162, 746.
13. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192.